

SVM: F(T)

B1: $C = 5^{3.98}$, $\epsilon = 0.11$; B2: $C = 5^{4.93}$, $\epsilon = 0.12$; B3: $C = 5^{3.97}$, $\epsilon = 0.52$

Components: —●— urban —●— rural —●— nourban —●— norural